

SERUM LEVEL OF VASCULAR ENDOTHELIAL GROWTH FACTOR AS A DIAGNOSTIC AND PROGNOSTIC INDICATOR FOR COLORECTAL CANCER

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AABSTRACT

The primary treatment for colorectal cancer, which is a leading cause of cancer-related deaths, is still drastic surgery, although an early detection is necessary. Carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and carbohydrate antigen are the serum indicators that are being employed in clinical practice for colorectal cancer (CA19-9). Due to their low sensitivity and specificity, both are only utilized for surveillance and as prognostic indicators for disease-free survival. They are not employed for diagnostic or screening reasons. Thus, a serum sign that aids in early detection is desperately needed. Targeting angiogenesis has been demonstrated to be a successful anti-tumor strategy, as it plays a crucial role in the growth and progression of tumors. One of the main stimulants of angiogenesis is vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), whose serum concentration has been linked to a wide range of human cancers and may serve as a prognostic indicator for solid tumors. The purpose of this study was to examine VEGF expression in patients with colorectal cancer (CRC) and compare the results to the clinicopathologic characteristics of the patients. The serum levels of CEA and CA19-9 were compared to the VEGF levels in 68 patients and 10 healthy controls. The findings demonstrated a significant correlation between the levels of CEA and CA19-9 and an elevated serum level of VEGF in CRC patients. In conclusion, measuring VEGF serum levels can help identify patients with colorectal cancer (CRC) and pave the road for the targeted treatment of CRC patients with VEGF inhibitors.

Keywords: Rectal Carcinoma; VEGF; CEA; CA19-9

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1. INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is one of the major causes of cancer death worldwide, accounting for more than 150,000 new cases and 55,000 deaths in the United States every year and 125,000 mortalities each year in Europe¹. Worldwide, approximately one million new cases of colorectal cancer (CRC) are diagnosed each year, with nearly 500,000 deaths attributed to this disease annually².

The main line of therapy for patients with localized disease is radical surgery, followed by adjuvant chemotherapy³. However, a significant proportion of patients present get recurrence and patients with the same tumor stages may show different outcomes, indicating that the conventional staging procedures may be unable to precisely predict Cancer prognosis⁴. Therefore, it is necessary to search for new prognostic factors capable of identifying high-risk patients and of modulating therapeutic options⁵.

For colorectal carcinoma (CRC), serum markers in current clinical use are carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) and carbohydrate antigen (CA19-9). Both markers are widely used during surveillance and as prognostic measures for disease-free survival but not for diagnostic or screening purposes because of insufficient sensitivity and specificity⁶⁻⁸

Angiogenesis, a physiological process involving the growth of new blood vessels from pre-existing vessels, plays a key role in tumor growth and progression. Targeting of tumor angiogenesis has been shown to be an effective approach to suppress tumor growth and metastasis^{9,10}

Tumor development is possible due to formation of new blood vessels. Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is one of the major factors that stimulate angiogenesis and its concentration could be a prognostic marker in solid tumors^{11,12}. VEGF expression has been described in a large variety of human malignancies e.g. lung, breast, colon.¹³⁻¹⁵ Some studies suggested that expression of VEGF correlates with poor prognosis and metastasis¹⁵⁻¹⁷ so, VEGF has been demonstrated to be a major contributor to angiogenesis^{18,19}. Thereby, Serum VEGF levels are elevated in colorectal cancer patients²⁰.

Rectal bleeding, a persistent alteration in bowel habits, and anemia in the absence of other gastrointestinal symptoms are the most often reported symptoms and indicators of colorectal cancer (44% of cases). Forty percent of cases show stomach pain as the second most prevalent symptom. A partial obstruction, peritoneal dissemination, or intestinal perforation resulting in widespread peritonitis might all be the source of this pain²¹ on the hand, it was added that some symptoms do not become apparent until the cancer is far advanced. Approximately 55% of patient present with advanced colorectal cancer (spread to the lymph nodes, metastasized to other organs, or is so locally invasive that surgery to remove the primary tumor alone is unlikely to be sufficient for cure).

Survival rates in individuals with colorectal cancer have increased substantially in the past few years, possibly as a result of early diagnosis and improved treatment. Although substantial information about risk factors exists, about 75% of diagnosis is in patients with no apparent risk factors other than the old age.²²

Proangiogenic factors include VEGFs, fibroblast growth factors, platelet-derived growth factors, insulin-like growth factor, and transforming growth factors; antiangiogenic factors include thrombospondin-1, angiostatin, and endostatin. Physiologic angiogenesis is only observed transiently, during embryogenesis, wound healing, and reproductive functions in adults.²³ Normal and pathologic angiogenic processes differ in the tightly regulated balance of proangiogenic and antiangiogenic signals.

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The formation of a network of blood vessels that enters malignant growths and supplies nutrients, oxygen, and waste products is known as tumor angiogenesis. The process of tumor angiogenesis essentially begins with the release of chemicals by malignant tumor cells, which alert the surrounding normal host tissue. By activating specific genes in the host tissue, this signaling promotes the creation of new blood vessels by causing the production of proteins.²⁴ This study looked at the expression of VEGF in patients with colorectal cancer (CRC) and compared the results to the clinicopathologic characteristics of the patients.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study was carried on 68 histologically confirmed for colorectal carcinoma patients underwent elective surgery at Gastroenterology center, Mansoura University: 39 males and 29 females with ages ranged from 24-74 years. Ten healthy individuals (6 males and 4 females) of matched age and sex were used as a control group.

Patients were subjected to clinical evaluation through history taking, clinical examination, endoscopic evaluation, radiological evaluation and laboratory investigation that included liver function tests (serum albumin, serum bilirubin, ALT and AST, and serum creatinine), complete blood picture and serum levels for CEA and CA19.9. All patients were confirmed to have CRC by histopathological examination with grading and staging according to Dukes' staging system for colorectal cancer.

Blood Samples for Patients and Controls:

1-2 mls venous blood were withdrawn from each subject by aseptic venipuncture from an antecubital vein and were left to clot in plain polypropylene tube at 25 C for 30 minutes, then the separated serum was used for the assay before centrifugation for 15 minutes approximately 1000 × g. serum were removed and samples were stored at $\leq -20^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the following:

Quantitative determination of Human VEGF concentrations by enzyme linked immune sorbent assay.

Principles of the Assay

The kit measures the amount of human VEGF in the sample, coats microtiter plate wells with purified human VEGF antibody to create solid-phase antibody, and then adds VEGF to the wells. Following thorough washing, the combined antibody and goat anti-human enzyme-labeled antibody form an antibody-antigen-enzyme-antibody complex. When substrate is added, it turns blue. A sulphuric acid solution is added to stop the HRP enzyme-catalyzed process, and the color shift is detected spectrophotometrically at 450 nm. The optical density (O.D.) of the samples is then compared to the standard curve to ascertain the concentration of VEGF in the samples.

Assay Procedure

Set 10 Standard wells on the microtiter plate coated, started with 100 μl in the first and the second well with serial dilution in every two consecutive wells of the rest 8 wells (density: 900pg/ml, 600pg/ml, 300pg/ml, 150pg/ml, 75pg/ml). Set blank sample wells separately (blank comparison wells don't add Sample and Enzyme Conjugate. Add Sample dilution 40 μl to sample well, then add Sample 10 μl (sample final dilution is 5-fold), add sample to wells, don't touch the well wall as far as possible, and gently mix. Incubate: After closing plate with Closure plate membrane, incubate for 30 mins at 37°C. Prepare solution: 20-fold wash solution diluted 20-fold with distilled water and reserve. Manual Washing: Remove incubation mixture by aspirating contents of the plate into a sink or proper waste container.

Using a squirt bottle, fill each well completely with wash solution, then aspirate contents of the plate into a sink or proper waste container. Repeat this procedure four more times for a total five washes. After final wash, invert plate, and blot dry by hitting plate onto absorbent paper or paper towels until no moisture appears. (Note: Hold the sides of the plate frame firmly when washing the plate to assure that all strips remain securely in frame. Incubate and wash. Color: Add 50 μ l Substrate Stop the reaction by adding 50 μ l Stop solution to each well. Mix well. Determine the optical density of each well within 15 mins by a microplate reader set to 450 nm.

Calculations

The standard density as the horizontal, the O.D value for the vertical, the standard curve was drawn on graph paper, It find out the corresponding density according to the sample O.D value by the sample curve, multiplied by dilution factor, calculate the sample density, multiplied by the dilution factor, the result is the sample actual density. A standard curve were constructed by plotting the mean optical density for each standard on the y-axis against the concentration on the x-axis and draw a best fit curve through the points on the graph. The best fit line were determined by regression analysis.

Statistical Analysis

Data entry and analysis were performed using SPSS statistical package version 10 (SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The quantitative data were presented as a mean and standard deviation, and the qualitative data were presented as number and percentage. The chi-square (χ^2) was used to find the association between row and column variables of qualitative data.

The threshold of significance is fixed at 5% level (P value). P value of > 0.05 indicates non-significant results; P value of < 0.05 indicates a significant result

3. RESULTS

This study included 68 patients with colorectal carcinoma, 39 males and 29 females, male to female ratio 1.34/1 (57% and 43%). The age ranges from (74 –24) years with median age 53 ± 12.26 years. The clinical analysis of the cases included in the study revealed that the mostly affected site is rectum (n=33) followed by distal colon (n=24) and lastly the proximal colon (n=11). Most of the patients presented with bleeding per rectum (82%) and disturbed bowel habit (70%). The analysis of VEGF, CA 19-9 and CEA in relation to age and gender revealed no significant difference. The pathologic examination of the tumors resected from the patients revealed 49 (72.1%) classic adenocarcinoma, 18 mucoid adenocarcinoma (26.5%) and 1 squamous cell carcinoma. According to the pathological grade of differentiation, grade I (12, 17.6%), grade II (47, 69%) and grade III (8, 11.8%). The lymph node status of the resected specimens revealed 19 (28%) cases with secondary nodal metastasis. The correlation between the serum levels of CEA, CA19.9 and VEGF revealed significant positive correlation in the studied cases. Correlation between the lymph node status and the levels of CEA, CA19-9 and VEGF revealed no significant correlation as shown in figure 2. There was no significant correlation between the type of carcinoma and the levels of CEA, CA19-9 and VEGF as shown in figure 3. The correlation between the pathologic grade of carcinoma and the levels of CEA, CA19-9 and VEGF revealed no significant correlation as shown in figure 4.

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Figure 1: Positive correlation between VEGF serum level and serum level of CEA ($p<0.05$).

Figure 2: correlation between VEGF, CA 19-9 and CEA serum levels and the lymph node status.

Figure 3: correlation between VEGF, CA 19-9 and CEA serum levels and the pathologic type of carcinoma.

Figure 4: correlation between VEGF, CA 19-9 and CEA serum levels and the pathologic grade of carcinoma.

4. DISCUSSION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most common cancer and the second leading cause of cancer-related death in the Western World. The cause of CRC is likely to be multi-factorial, and associations have been reported with family history, diet and alcohol. Failure to define a primary cause of CRC prevents the primary prevention programs, thus, attention has therefore focused on screening programs²⁵. Angiogenesis is essential for tumor growth and metastasis. Cancer is a multistep process resulting in aggressive growth potential²⁶. An elevated level of a tumor marker is a non specific indicator of cancer; however, it can be useful in the follow up of treated patients²⁷.

The aim of this study was to investigate the expression of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) in colorectal cancer (CRC) patients; and correlate the findings with the patients' clinicopathologic features.

We found that range of age of the studied patients was from 24 to 74 years and the mean age was 50 ± 12.26 years. This result coincided with Khafagy *et al.*²⁸ who found that the median age of the Egyptian patients with colorectal cancer was 45 years with range 17 to 78 years; on the other hand, It was founded that the mean age of CRC patients was 59.5 ± 12.6 years.²⁹ Another large study (607 patients) revealed that the mean age for colorectal cancer patients was 43.1 ± 9.3 years.³⁰

The present study showed slight increase in incidence of CRC in males than females. This was in agreement with studies which stated that CRC is more common in males.^{31,32} On the other hand, there was a study stated that CRC is more common in females.³² Controversy between results could be explained by large number in cases in Jover (754 patients) and Aljebreen (113 patients) studies.

Moderately differentiated tumor (grade II) represents the commonest histopathologic type (69.1%) found in this study. This was in accordance with Gryfe *et al.*³⁰ who found moderately differentiated tumor in about 69%. Also, there was a study reported the same which stated that histopathology of CRC showed that 56% of tumors were moderately differentiated.³² In the present study, Adenocarcinoma was the commonest histopathologic type (72.1%). This result coincided with Weitz *et al.*³⁴ who found that adenocarcinoma represents (85%) and Fenoglio³⁵ who found that adenocarcinoma represents (90%) of all studied patients. In this study, most of cases presented at stage C. This results in accordance with Abou-zeid *et al.*³⁶ incidence who found that Dukes' C represent 58% among CRC patients. This result also was matching with the studies that stated that 68% of CRC lesions were stage C.³²

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Serum CEA levels can be determined accurately and reproducibly, and for this reason, this marker was believed to have a potential as a serological screening tool for early detection.³⁷ The present study showed that serum CEA increases with Dukes' stages and grades. These results were in agreement with studies that stated that the level of CEA increased with stages and grades of differentiation of tumor.³⁷⁻³⁹ and there were significant high CEA levels in CRC patients with L.N metastasis which matched with the studies that reported that high preoperative serum CEA levels, and was significantly correlated with the depth of tumor invasion, and the status of lymph nodes metastasis.^{37,39}

On the other hand, CA19.9 cannot be recommended for early diagnosis of CRC. As regards sensitivity, although elevated levels of CA19.9 have been reported in as many as 75% of patients with advanced CRC, most studies suggested that it is a less sensitive marker than CEA for CRC.⁴⁰ There was a significant increase in serum CA19.9 level in CRC patients. This result was matched with studies that report that both CA19.9 level and sensitivity increased with increasing Dukes' stage of disease.⁴¹ and also, with that stated that serum CA19.9 level is increased with stage of tumor.³⁹

In comparison to controls, this study showed a highly significant expression of VEGF in the peripheral blood of CRC patients. This finding is consistent with research showing greater serum VEGF levels in colorectal cancer patients compared to control participants.

⁴² Serum VEGF showed highly significant elevated levels in CRC patient groups. This result indicates that VEGF expression is increased with advancing Dukes' stages in CRC patients, which is coincided with the studies that reported that VEGF expression was significantly positively correlated with Dukes' stages.⁴³ VEGF expression increased with the progression of colorectal carcinogenesis classified by Dukes' stages and patients with the highest VEGF expression had a significantly poorer prognosis with earlier recurrence and death than those with intermediate or low expression levels.⁴⁴ This result was in consistent with another study which stated that VEGF expression at the deepest site of tumor invasion can be a useful predictor of poor prognosis in advanced CRC and show a close relation to angiogenesis.⁴⁵ The high VEGF expression, which was correlated with Dukes' stages and the presence of distant metastasis could be explained by high molecular alterations that occur in advanced colon cancer. Moreover, this result was in agreement with studies that stated that VEGF plays an important role in progression, invasion and spread of colorectal cancer by influencing the proliferation and migration of endothelial cells and there have been attempts to inhibit VEGF synthesis in patients with advanced colorectal cancer with anti-VEGF therapy.⁴⁶

VEGF was significantly positively correlated with CEA levels and this result was in agreement with studies that performed that quantitative evaluation of VEGF and CEA content on protein extracts obtained from tissue biopsies from 69 CRC patients and found that VEGF was significantly correlated with CEA content of either tumor tissue or corresponding normal mucosa.⁴⁷ the diagnostic sensitivity of VEGF for colorectal carcinoma was higher than the sensitivity of CEA, and in combination both markers the sensitivity to predict colorectal carcinoma was higher than each marker alone.⁴⁸

Serum VEGF and CA19.9 in CRC patients showed a highly significant correlation. This result was in a agreement with the studies that assessed plasma VEGF in patients with CRC before surgery and found an increase in VEGF with a strong positive correlation with metastatic spread and serum CA19.9.⁴⁶

Also, there was positive correlation between CEA and CA19.9 levels in studied patients and this was in agreement with the studies which stated that there was a significant positive correlation between the plasma CEA, and CA19.9 levels and the CRC stage (Dukes' classification).^{50,51}

It was postulated that at time of diagnosis of CRC 50.6% of the patients had elevated serum of CEA and 29.6% of CA19.9. In combination of both antigens this elevation was in 54.3% of CRC patients. The common use of CEA and CA19.9 was efficacious in identification of patients at high risk. The combination assay of CEA and CA19.9 did not cause a significant increase of sensitivity in diagnosis CRC.²⁵

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